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Pilot Methodology

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Deliverable Abstract

This document describes the Pilot Methodology that will be applied to perform user-testing and assess discipline-specific fitness of the outputs developed within the EOSC EDEN project. The testing will be performed by teams representing the seven early-adopter disciplines of the EOSC EDEN project, following the guidelines outlined here. This document covers the full testing process from preparing testing materials and generating evidence, through to evaluation. Testing teams will assess outputs based on multiple feedback dimensions and user-acceptance criteria. The criteria and the methodology will be defined and refined iteratively in collaboration with the testing and development teams.

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v.1.0	22/12/2025	Final editorial check and submitted version	Same as above and Anu Märkälä

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CPP	Core Preservation Process
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FIDELIS	FIDELIS: Establishing A European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
MSx	Milestone number x
Mxy	Month xy
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
Tx.y	Task x.y
UJM(s)	User Journey Map(s)

WP	Work Package
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Executive Summary

EOSC EDEN is an EU-funded project that aims at supporting and promoting digital preservation practices at the European and national levels by enriching the EOSC ecosystem with tools, services, and standards designed in a user-centric way [1]. As the project will develop novel outputs, both practical (tools, services, metrics) and conceptual (models and frameworks) in nature, multiple testing phases to evaluate them have been designed in the conception of the project. During this testing, the outputs of the project will be assessed by teams representing the seven disciplines involved as early adopters in EOSC EDEN: Climate Simulations, Earth & Environmental Sciences, Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences.

This deliverable presents the methodology that the testing teams will employ to pilot the EOSC EDEN outputs and to provide feedback to the development teams, and serves as a lightweight framework to guide the testing teams. In this document, we outline the expected outputs to be tested, together with supporting assets such as documentation and use cases. Moreover, we describe the operational aspects of the testing, including user acceptance criteria and feedback dimensions and delivery.

1 Introduction

The EOSC EDEN project has the ambitious objective of enhancing digital preservation practices and strategies at the European and national level. To achieve this, EOSC EDEN will deliver a range of key outputs, both operational such as tools, metrics and support material, and more conceptual, such as frameworks and policies [1]. These outputs will be tested for verification and improvement during several testing phases, each triggered by releases from the Work Packages (WPs). The testing will be performed by teams representing seven disciplines chosen as early adopters in the project, i.e.: Climate Simulations, Earth & Environmental Sciences, Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences & Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences. Feedback will be delivered in a timely manner back to the WPs to allow improvement of their outputs. The testing will be organised and performed by Task 3.2, which is dedicated to validating the EOSC EDEN outputs.

In this document, we outline the methodology that we will follow in performing the testing. The key results of the testing are the acceptance measurements of the EOSC EDEN outputs, evaluated for each discipline according to well defined acceptance criteria. The evaluation of these criteria will lead to a sliding scale of adoption capability for each output and discipline.

In elaborating this Pilot Methodology, we have adhered to a set of principles: the methodology should be structured but flexible, allowing for approaches that adapt to output type, complexity and project capacity; the pilots should generate traceable evidence linked to user acceptance criteria; the testing should have ample disciplinary coverage, including all seven early adopter disciplines, and the methodology should allow for iterative refinement, accommodating course correction when necessary. We envision that this approach will provide early-stage quality assurance, reveal potential usability issues, help prioritise improvements, and ensure that the project deliverables and milestones meet diverse end-user needs.

This document also highlights the expected output of T3.3; a Support Kit to guide and support new users in adopting the results of EOSC EDEN. This Support Kit is not included in the Pilot Methodology, as it is not bound to be tested during the discipline-oriented pilots, but its development will be substantially supported by the outcome and insights of the pilots.

Finally, we emphasise that this methodology has been designed while the development work was still in its planning phase. Thus, the methodology has been ideated a priori, with the information contained in the EOSC EDEN Grant Agreement [1] and with the initial knowledge of the first 6-8 months of the project. Consequently, we have sought to create a methodology framework that is complete to support our future work, while flexible enough to allow for modifications, refinements and adaptations as the project progresses and evolves.

Most of this deliverable is based on the EOSC EDEN Grant Agreement, project-internal documentation and conversations between the different WPs.

Structure of this document

Since this deliverable primarily supports internal project processes, this document is organised into two main sections: one for WP1 and the other for WP2, which are the work packages primarily responsible for delivering the EOSC EDEN outputs. This parallel structure allows readers to access complete methodological guidance for their specific work package without cross-referencing multiple sections. While this approach includes some repetition of common elements, such as operational procedures and feedback mechanisms, it ensures each section remains self-contained and hence enhances readability and practical application.

This document is structured as follows: In Section 1, we show a diagram that visually represents the workflow of the Pilot Methodology, and then describe the User Journey Maps, a previous output of T3.2 that relates to the Pilot Methodology. Sections 2 and 3 present the methodology for the outputs of WP1 and WP2, respectively. Both sections have an identical structure: We first describe the "releases" that each WP needs to hand off to T3.2 for testing. The release contains the produced output of the WP and supporting assets (such as documentation and use cases). We then list discipline-specific material (e.g., test datasets, other use cases, etc.) that will be added to the release to create a testing package for the testing teams. In the following (sub)sections, we describe the practical procedures that will be employed for the testing, followed by guidelines to formulate the acceptance criteria, which inform the assessment of the WP outputs. Finally, we list all the aspects to consider when giving feedback to be delivered back to the WP.

In Section 4, we list points of interaction with WP3 and conclude in Section 5 with some closing remarks and a table that summarises the steps of the methodology.

1.1 Pilot Methodology Diagram

Figure 1 – Pilot Methodology diagram. In purple the elements related to WP1 or WP2, in orange the ones related to WP3 and T3.2 in particular. The diagram and the sections of this document follow the timeline of each iteration of the Pilot Methodology, which is triggered at each WP release.

In Figure 1, we show a diagram that represents the workflow anticipated for the Pilot Methodology:

- After each release, the responsible WP will hand off the developed output and supporting assets (documentation, selected requirements) to T3.2 (see Sections 2.1.1, 2.1.2 for WP1 and 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 for WP2).
- T3.2 will then add other material when needed, such as test datasets and user journeys (see Sections 2.1.3 and 3.1.3 for WP1 and WP2, respectively), and hand off the resulting testing package to the testing teams. When possible, the same additional material will be used to test the outputs of WP1 and WP2 and for the testing at the two different TRLs.

- The testing teams (see Sections 2.2.1 and 3.2.1) will perform the pilot following the practical methodology described in Sections 2.2 and 3.2 (for WP1 and WP2, respectively).
- At the end of the testing period, the testing teams will deliver their feedback back to T3.2, where it will be processed, if necessary, and handed over to the development teams of WP1 and WP2 (see Sections 2.3, 2.4 for WP1 and 3.3, 3.4 for WP2).
- Finally, we include a feedback mechanism where T3.2 receives feedback on the Pilot Methodology both from the testing teams and WP1 and WP2, to enhance it for the next testing rounds (see Section 4.2).

1.2 Component Inventory

We propose to establish a Component Inventory¹ which will serve as a single source of truth for each output of the WPs, linking all relevant information included in or occurring during workflow, and as the location to gather and deliver feedback on each tested output to the development teams.

1.3 User Journey Maps

A User Journey Map (UJM) is a visualisation of the process that a user goes through in order to accomplish a certain goal. UJMs are used to visualise the experience that a user has while interacting with a tool, a service or a framework (the “touch points”) and to capture the frustrations or negative emotions (the “pain points”) that they experience during this process. In the context of this Pilot Methodology, UJMs allow for a visual identification of the pain points experienced by users interacting with digital preservation tools, services and frameworks. They are, therefore, a useful instrument to assess the user acceptance of project outputs and provide feedback: A tool/service/framework is considered “successful” if it effectively helps users resolve pain points in their journey.

The UJMs are a Milestone of the EOSC EDEN project (MS8). They were released in October 2025 and are at the time of writing available on the project-internal Wiki. UJMs will serve as discipline-specific, additional testing material. The UJMs represent a core component of the testing procedure, as they allow for contextualising the output to be tested in user-centric and discipline-specific workflows.

During the piloting, the UJMs will be updated and enriched with the information emerging from the testing itself. Connections between the WP releases and the UJMs - especially the pain points recorded in them - are going to be taken into account when providing feedback on the fitness for purpose of the tested outputs.

2 Testing Procedures for Work Package 1 Outputs

Work Package 1 is the core digital preservation work package. It collects stakeholder feedback (WP3, WP4), transforms it into actionable processes and requirements for implementation (WP2), and fosters community adoption (WP3, WP4). Its main aims and objectives focus on two areas: Firstly, it investigates existing frameworks, guidelines and practices for identification, selection, and appraisal of data for digital preservation by performing a landscape analysis to transform user needs into requirements (T1.1). Secondly, it establishes a framework to identify what data are candidates for digital preservation based on use, benefit, and quality (T1.2), and develops a Model for Reappraisal points along the data lifecycle (T1.3). The design of all tasks in WP1 relies on the Reuse Fitness Model (see Figure 2). This model forms the conceptual foundation of the EOSC EDEN project by describing quality pillars of digital objects against organisational capabilities and preservation objectives.

¹ The proposed Component Inventory could be hosted on the project-internal Wiki, as pages linking all information for each component e.g., use cases, documentation, code repositories, selected requirements, Jira/development tickets.

Figure 2: The Reuse Fitness Model: Information Object Reuse Fitness pillars and horizontal factors²

2.1 Testing Package

A testing package for project outputs of WP1 is composed by three elements:

- milestones and deliverables - the actual testing targets;
- supporting assets that supports the above;
- additional testing material as provided by the disciplinary experts to support piloting procedures tailored to discipline or data-type specific requirements.

2.1.1 Milestones and Deliverables

The Pilot Methodology will be triggered by the release of milestones MS2 and MS3 of WP1.

MS2 - Metrics for Information Object Re-Use Fitness - June 2026 (M18)

The main aim of T1.2 (running between November 2025 and June 2026) is the development of metrics for contextual and technical data quality as well as metadata quality that inform the definition of an information object's reuse. MS2 will inform each of the vertical pillars of the Reuse Fitness Model (Figure 2). It aims to provide a basic set of technical re-use fitness metrics, a minimum set for metadata completeness, and semantic quality markers. Throughout this deliverable, this output will be referred to as "Metrics".

MS3 - Model description of (re-)appraisal within a digital archive - February 2027 (M26)

The main aim of T1.1 is to integrate existing practices in identification, appraisal and selection with information object fitness levels in order to develop a Model for Reappraisal that facilitates their implementation into the data lifecycle management. Altogether, the model will support systematic and well-informed initial appraisal and, where appropriate, reappraisal procedures in order to ensure that the needs of the designated community and the preservation objectives are met. Throughout this deliverable, this output will be referred to as "Model for Reappraisal".

MS1 - Identification of core preservation processes for WP2 - August 2025 (M8)

At the time of writing, WP1 has already produced MS1 which contains definitions and descriptions of "Core Preservation Processes" (CPPs). The CPPs are specific actions that every Trustworthy Digital Archive should undertake in order to fulfil its digital preservation missions as evidenced in its preservation policy. All CPPs

² <https://eden-fidelis.eu/repositories-archives>

and their supporting materials (i.e., a glossary and a blank template) are publicly available³ together with a visual tool⁴ to help navigate and understand them.

Since the CPPs inform the methodology and structure of other project outputs, they hold a significant role in testing. For example, the development of the service registry as led by WP2 (see Section 3.1.1) and the UJMs as developed by WP3 (see Section 1.3) contain a mapping with the CPPs.

As the CPP development was scheduled ahead of the creation of the Pilot Methodology, their inclusion will follow a different procedure. It is anticipated that feedback on the relevance, applicability and understandability of the CPPs will evolve organically along with piloting procedures of other testing packages that have implemented them. In consultation with WP1, T3.2 will facilitate feedback that impacts the CPPs by leveraging exchange with disciplinary expert audiences as needed.

2.1.2 Supporting Assets

As defined in the data management plan [3], GitHub⁵ serves as the main platform to collaboratively edit and curate code produced within WP1. This ensures transparent version control, open contribution pathways, and continuous alignment with implementation activities in WP2 and piloting activities in WP3 and WP4. In addition, all materials developed by WP1 are supported by a glossary⁶ which ensures that terminology is used consistently within the WP and the wider project, and is aligned with established standards in the digital preservation community.

2.1.3 Additional Testing Material

To support the understandability and implementation of the WP1 outputs, disciplinary experts within T3.2 will provide a diversity of testing material drawn from different disciplines and data types e.g.: test datasets, scenario descriptions, use cases or specific policies and workflows that are characteristic of a discipline. Relevant UJMs will be included, to contextualise the testing material with discipline-specific cases and workflows and to evaluate the testing material against them, to consider its fitness for purpose from the point of view of the touch and pain points recorded in the UJMs.

Additionally, T3.2 will provide material that relates to the testing practice itself (e.g., standardised feedback forms or questionnaires).

Taken together, these materials will offer operational guidance for conducting appraisal and reappraisal, documenting metric application and evaluations, and structuring preservation decisions consistently and transparently.

Testing of Metrics for re-use fitness of information object

For the testing of the Metrics, we will need to provide test datasets or test digital objects with well known characteristics, to verify the applicability of the Metrics:

- Defining a digital object's reuse calls for diverse datasets as testing material, of such diversity that it tests the metrics and the acceptance criteria in all their "breadth" (i.e., do they capture all challenges that are necessary to capture?).
- The test dataset should be tailored to the quantity that the Metrics aim to calculate and evaluate and should be chosen with attention to several possible characteristics such as usage, data or file type,

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/16992452>

⁴ <https://cpp.fEOSC EDENv.csc.fi/>

⁵ <https://github.com/EOSC-EDEN>

⁶ <https://EOSC EDENnode.org/records/16992452>

size, age, metadata completeness, ethical or legal challenges and so on, again depending on the nature of the Metrics.

- It could be that one single test dataset cannot cover all the diversity needed to fully test the Metrics. We rely on the expertise of the disciplinary teams to identify test objects with the right characteristics.

Also, the UJMs contain discipline-specific example workflows where the fitness for use of a digital object is considered. Applying and evaluating the Metrics through the UJMs will allow their validity to be assessed.

Finally, discipline-specific use cases could support the testing teams in contextualising the application of the Metrics. These use cases can be extracted from the discipline-specific UJMs, but depending on the nature of the Metrics, additional use cases will be produced closer to the WP release.

Testing of Model for Reappraisal along Data Lifecycle

For testing the Model for Reappraisal, we would again need a sample digital object of known value (i.e., that we know must be continuously preserved) and test the reappraisal capability of the model on it:

- We should aim at “stress-testing” the Model with datasets of known value but lacking in some aspects, e.g., a digital object that cannot be reproduced and would be completely lost, but has very poor quality, and that cover a broad diversity, e.g., age, data type.
- In addition to the relevant UJMs and discipline-specific use cases, we may need to identify a test repository to test the full range of the Model, i.e., including repository policies and repository-level frameworks in the testing package.

We note that for reappraisal actions, existing, relevant discipline-specific policies and frameworks have been captured as touch points in the UJMs and we will include them in the test package as use cases, when necessary.

2.2 Pilot Procedure

In this section, we outline the operational procedures that will be employed for testing the WP1 outputs.

2.2.1 Testing Team Setup

T3.2 coordinates and participates in forming testing teams, designing testing protocols and ensuring representative engagement for both quantitative and qualitative deliverables. The members of T3.2 representing the seven disciplines will participate in the testing teams leveraging their domain expertise, while the members who do not represent one of the disciplines will cover coordination roles. The different functions the team members will cover, include:

- **Coordination and facilitation:** Configuring workflows with standardised reporting templates in coordination with WP1, distributing the testing package, conducting briefing sessions, planning and executing testing activities (e.g., workshops, asynchronous activities, interviews), and coordinating participant recruitment when broader community input is needed.
- **Evaluation:** Assessing the WP outputs through the testing package, against acceptance criteria (Section 2.3) and across feedback dimensions (Section 2.4). For quantitative outputs (metrics), members identify test datasets with known characteristics, apply metrics, verify calculations, and document results. For qualitative outputs (frameworks, models, guidelines), the testing team engages through scenario walkthroughs, structured interviews, and feasibility assessments to evaluate applicability and clarity. The goal of the evaluation is to also synthesise feedback and formulate recommendations for refinement.

- **Domain-specific validation:** Conducting relevance assessments, verifying alignment with discipline-specific needs and community standards across EOSC EDEN's seven early adopter disciplines, and identifying additional use cases for validation.

Additionally, WP1 provides oversight and guidance on frameworks, models, and metrics during testing cycles.

2.2.2 How Testing is Conducted

1. **Preparation:** Test scenarios are defined collaboratively with WP1, linking validation objectives (i.e. acceptance criterion, feedback) to the testing package. Relevant UJMs are selected and included in the testing package to guide the testing teams. Testing teams identify use cases and additional materials needed beyond WP1's supporting assets. The coordinating and facilitating team members conduct briefing sessions during WP1 handover, covering objectives, credentials, available resources, and submission procedures.
2. **Evidence Collection:** During testing, evidence (in the form of artefacts such as feedback forms, calculation logs, implementation examples, test datasets, screenshots, etc.) will be collected in a standardised and traceable way, enabling the development teams to connect findings to specific use cases and scenarios and inform future decisions.
3. **Review and Synthesis:** At the end of testing, the feedback will be organised by severity, scope and dimensions to facilitate systematic analysis, and aggregated when common patterns emerge. A summary report will be produced as a first line of information for the development teams of the testing outcome. Reports support the WP in prioritising evidence-driven improvements.

2.2.3 When Testing Occurs

Pilot testing starts right after each WP1 release. Depending on the complexity and priority, each cycle runs for about 4-8 weeks. After the WP1 release, handover, and pilot preparation steps, testing follows a four phase iterative cycle tailored to the testing package:

1. **Assessment:** The testing team assesses the testing package against acceptance criteria and across feedback dimensions, 2-4 weeks depending on output complexity.
2. **Synthesis:** Test results are organised and aggregated during two weeks before handover to WP1.
3. **Revision:** WP1 implements changes, including calculation refinements and framework clarity improvements.
4. **Validation:** For outputs that do not satisfy the acceptance criteria and go through a revision, a small scale reassessment to verify the improvements will be carried out (i.e., start from 1 or complete the cycle).

Testing within each discipline or test package proceeds independently to respect project timelines and capacity. Synchronisation points (e.g., workshops, webinars, reviews) promote alignment and knowledge sharing. Regular task meetings (e.g., bi-weekly) track progress, address technical challenges, and support participants. These sessions facilitate alignment on scope, course corrections, and resource allocation. T3.2 coordinating and facilitating team members may adjust modality in response to emerging patterns or unforeseen challenges.

2.2.4 Where Testing Takes Place

Platform selection should be geared towards prioritising existing tools to minimise technical overhead, ensure participant familiarity, and simplify access management when testing involves public or broader audiences. The EOSC EDEN Jira platform is used to manage tickets with project defined standardised templates, GitHub handles code tracking aligned with WP1 workflow, Confluence and Google Docs support

documentation and workshop materials, and EOSC EDEN chat channels and email lists facilitate communication. When necessary, sandboxes and test environments are going to be provided, facilitated by WP5, for evaluators to assess testing packages.

2.3 Acceptance Criteria

As we will see, for WP1 and its outputs, acceptance criteria are more difficult to define compared to the case of WP2 since they are a concept taken from software development: The criteria for acceptance of a tool are defined consequently to the selection of requirements to be developed, with a clear connection between requirement - and therefore, function of a tool - and acceptance criterion - verification that the function is achieved.

Nonetheless, to achieve a well-structured and verifiable testing outcome for the WP1 outputs, we will outline principles to follow when defining acceptance criteria. We stress that these criteria will be co-developed with WP1 as soon as the outputs (Metrics and Model for Reappraisal) are more defined in their development process.

The acceptance criteria will help the testing teams to assess whether the WP output is delivering on its promise. To do so for WP1, the following three criteria will inform the assessment: understandability, applicability, and relevance:

- **Understandability:** Target users should understand the importance of the WP1 outputs and how to apply them in their discipline-specific workflows.
- **Applicability:** Target users and communities must be able to actually use the outputs in their context. This means that the outputs should be applicable by the seven early adopter disciplines (i.e., Metrics should be possible to calculate in a straightforward way).
- **Relevance:** Target users should evaluate if the output being tested is relevant for their case or discipline. E.g., users can identify the benefits of the outputs for their respective working environment and consider their potential implementation into their discipline-specific workflows as useful.

Evaluation of these Criteria will likely lead to a sliding (Likert⁷) scale of adoption capability for each output of WP1 and discipline. Depending on the outcome of the testing and the scores of understandability and applicability for the seven disciplines, the testing could lead to a rejection of the developed output (e.g., if the Metrics cannot be applied by most of the disciplines) or to its acceptance. The latter may come with caveats that could be either addressed by the development teams, refining the output, or via the T3.3 Support Kit. For example, if only one of the seven disciplines encounters issues in the application of the tested output, this may be solved with an increased focus on this discipline/workflow in the Support Kit. The results of the acceptance criteria evaluation for each output will be provided to the development teams via the proposed Component Inventory (see Section 1.2).

On top of these general guidelines, we will co-develop more specific acceptance criteria depending on the shape of the WP1 outputs (e.g., validity, reliability, completeness).

⁷A Likert scale is a psychometric scale usually invoked in surveys to measure attitudes. In this context, we will adopt it to measure success or adoption capability of an output/metric, typically by assigning numerical values to qualitative descriptions (1: not capable to 5: fully capable). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Likert_scale

2.4 Feedback Dimensions

In this section, we describe how feedback about any aspect that is not contemplated in the acceptance criteria will be provided. We divide our feedback dimensions into two main categories that reflect the type of item assessed, i.e. “Metrics and Model for Reappraisal”, and “Guidelines and Documentations”.

We further mention that we aim at gathering more *qualitative* feedback on WP1, when compared with feedback on WP2, considering the rather conceptual nature of the outputs in this first WP. Alignment with the Reuse Fitness Model (Figure 2), the UJMs and the CPPs will also be considered during feedback work.

In what follows, we provide a limited number of examples to contextualise the feedback procedure, all while being aware that the shape and nature of the actual feedback will depend on the specific characteristics of the output considered.

2.4.1 Metrics and Model for Reappraisal

MS2 - Metrics for Information Object Re-Use Fitness

Feedback will be given on how valuable and accurate the metrics are from a general as well as discipline-specific research point of view and what can be improved. From a repository manager perspective, we will also provide information about the threshold values of the different metrics, including the possibility of their automated computation. Examples for illustration:

- How effective are the metrics in evaluating metadata quality (e.g., descriptive/ administrative/ technical metadata)?
- Are the metrics facilitating decision-making?
- Are the threshold values adequate for each discipline?

MS3 - Model description of (re-)appraisal within a digital archive

Feedback will be given on metric descriptions and whether these conform with the current digital archive capabilities and the needs of the designated community. Feedback will also be given on the general characteristics of the Model for Reappraisal. Examples for illustration:

- Are the changes feasible to implement in practice?
- What is the impact if these changes are not considered? Is the Model unnecessarily complex?

2.4.2 Guidelines and Documentation

For all guidelines and documentation produced in WP1, feedback will be given on several levels. Examples for illustration:

- readability, including structure, verbosity, distribution format and reading time;
- understandability, including comprehensiveness and precision;
- completeness, including level of detail.

Also the content of the guidelines and documentation will be analysed, including the coverage of discipline-specific aspects when relevant.

2.4.3 Delivery of Feedback

After feedback is produced by the testing teams, it will be checked and edited by the test coordinators, following a standardised feedback form. The feedback will be delivered to the development teams via the Component Inventory (Section 1.2).

3 Testing procedure for WP 2 outputs

WP2 enriches EOSC with user-centric tools and services for long-term access and preservation, automating and federating specialised curation and preservation tasks and standardising content submission, exchange, and dissemination between trustworthy repositories and archives. It is structured into three tightly coupled tasks:

- T2.1 defines the system requirements and technical specifications, translating validated user needs into an architecture and interoperability blueprint aligned with EOSC criteria and relevant community recommendations.
- T2.2 develops the operational services, namely i) a registry with selection guidance that harmonises and extends existing catalogues of trustworthy repositories and preservation services, ii) API specifications for discovery and service invocation, and iii) internally developed reference implementations for curation and preservation services, while integrating external services where appropriate.
- T2.3 standardises and implements interoperable content exchange by specifying and testing common APIs and package formats, providing crosswalks where multiple standards are in use, and publishing compliance test results to the registry.

These tasks are executed and validated through use cases spanning the EOSC ecosystem (institutional, national, regional, European, thematic, academic, non-profit, commercial) and discipline-oriented pilots by the seven early adopter disciplines, producing reusable reference implementations, configuration profiles, and a Support Kit.

3.1 Testing Package

The testing package for WP2 is composed of three elements:

- the outputs of the Work Package, which are the actual testing targets, in the form of project milestones and deliverables;
- with their supporting assets; and
- additional testing material provided by the disciplinary teams, which are often discipline- or data-type specific.

3.1.1 Milestones and Deliverables

The pilot is triggered at each WP release, which in the case of WP2 are two iterations of development of the same outputs, at two different TRLs:

- MS5 - First release (MVP: TRL4) of registry, deposit guidance, and automated curation services, use case service implementation - March 2026 (M15);
- MS7 - Beta Release (TRL6) of registry, deposit and curation platform, use case service implementations - January 2027 (M25).

A final report (D2.3) consolidating the project output with regard to the registry, services and selection guidance is due in October 2027 and will not be tested, given the closeness of the release date to the end of the project.

Given the milestone timeline, the Pilot Methodology applied to WP2 will reflect two rounds of testing: The first round of testing will be dedicated to verify that the work is on the right track and to focus the subsequent development, while the second round will evaluate the services and registry more fully and broadly.

We note, however, that in practical terms the development of the individual services will presumably follow a more agile approach with frequent iterations and updates. At the time of writing, initial software development has begun within the EOSC EDEN GitHub⁸ and associated repositories⁹. It can be expected that these will be the main access point to the developed services, hence these online repositories will form another, crucial part of a majority of testing packages. We will maintain close alignment between WP2 and WP3 during the development process to reach a smooth handover at the WP2 releases.

3.1.2 Supporting Assets

WP2 defines technical specifications and user scenarios for each service, essential for defining user acceptance criteria, and these will be included in the testing package. EOSC EDEN uses Jira for development tracking (requirements, specifications, implementation) which, while not part of the testing package, will be the source of truth for information and feedback.

Comprehensive, up-to-date user-facing documentation (e.g., access, configuration, API, usage guides, limitations) and relevant developer notes are required for every tested component. This documentation must enable disciplinary testers to understand the component's purpose and usage, including example workflows and error handling. Documentation should be version-controlled, reusable, and include clear versioning and change logs to link feedback unambiguously.

3.1.3 Additional Testing Material

To support the understandability and implementation of the WP2 outputs, the disciplinary experts within the testing teams will provide a diversity of testing material drawn from different disciplines. This will in particular allow for user-testing from a discipline-specific point of view and help contextualise the more complex services:

- The test datasets will be chosen depending on the characteristics of the tool and service to be tested.
 - For the first WP2 release at TRL4, the tools will be tested for their core functionalities and the test datasets should be chosen accordingly.
 - For TRL6 instead, we should aim at “stress-testing” the WP2 outputs, employing datasets that have a wide range of characteristics in terms of e.g., (meta)data completeness and quality, size, access conditions, ethical or legal challenges.
- To test the registry of services with guidance, the testing teams will in addition provide discipline- and data-type specific use cases and workflows to test the validity of the registry in a broad variety of scenarios.

⁸ <https://github.com/EOSC-EDEN>

⁹ e.g. <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher>

We will further include the relevant UJMs, which contain the pertinent touch and pain points, to contextualise the testing material with discipline-specific cases and workflows and to evaluate the testing material against them. Based on the complexity of the service to be tested, it might be advisable for the testing teams to set up specific UJMs for their test case.

Finally, T3.2 will provide material that relates to the testing practice itself (e.g., standardised feedback forms or questionnaires).

These materials will offer operational guidance for conducting appraisal, documenting tools application and evaluations in a consistent and transparent manner.

3.2 Pilot Procedure

In this section, we outline the operational procedures that will be employed for testing the WP2 outputs.

3.2.1 Testing Team Setup

T3.2 coordinates and participates in forming testing teams, designing testing protocols and ensuring representative engagement at both TRL levels. The members of T3.2 representing the seven disciplines will participate in the testing teams leveraging their domain expertise, while the members who do not represent one of the disciplines will cover coordination roles. The different functions the team members will cover, include:

- **Coordination and facilitation:** Configuring Jira/GitHub/Docs workflows (in coordination with WP2), establishing access permissions, distributing the testing package, conducting briefing sessions, planning and executing testing activities (workshops, webinars, surveys), and coordinating participant recruitment through WP4/FIDELIS for TRL6.
- **Evaluation:** T3.2 members independently assess service functionality, synthesise tickets/logs/surveys, and formulate recommendations for refinement. TRL4 evaluation draws from consortium institutions; TRL6 may include broader community participants recruited through WP4/FIDELIS partnership.
- **Domain-specific validation:** Conducting relevance assessments, verifying alignment with discipline-specific workflows and preservation practices across the seven EOSC EDEN early adopter disciplines, and identifying additional use cases and requirements beyond WP2's technical specifications.

Additionally, the WP2 development team provides technical guidance, clarifies functional specifications, participates in testing coordination meetings (especially for TRL6), and integrates feedback into development sprints.

3.2.2 How Testing Is Conducted

1. **Preparation:** Test scenarios are defined collaboratively with WP2, linking validation objectives to the testing package. Testing teams identify use cases and additional materials needed beyond WP2's technical specifications. The coordination and facilitation team conducts briefing sessions during WP2 handover, covering objectives, crEOSC EDENTials, available resources, and submission procedures.
2. **Evidence Collection:** During testing, evidence will be collected through standardised artefacts (such as logs, calculation results, service interaction examples, test datasets, screenshots, and URLs¹⁰) submitted by evaluators. The validation approach distinguishes between TRL4 and TRL6 testing. Structured assessment questions guide both evaluation processes, organised systematically by user

¹⁰ Uniform Resource Locator

goals and service capabilities.

This approach ensures full traceability, as observations, survey responses, and recommendations link to specific artefacts and assessment questions, enabling WP2 to trace findings to testing and inform development decisions.

3. **Review and Synthesis:** At the end of testing, the feedback will be organised by severity, scope and dimensions to facilitate systematic analysis, and aggregated when common patterns emerge. A summary report will be produced as the first line of information for the development teams of the testing outcome. Reports support WP2 in prioritising evidence-driven improvements.
4. **Iteration and Feedback Loop:** Test results can flow directly into development processes through integrated ticketing/issue based workflow, creating structured feedback channels between testing teams and developers. This continuous dialogue enables rapid iteration, i.e., once modifications are implemented, retesting verifies that issues are resolved, with particular attention to critical functional gaps identified at TRL4. Decisions about service readiness and progression reference the acceptance criteria detailed in Section 3.3.

3.2.3 When Testing Occurs

After WP2 release and pilot preparation, testing proceeds through a four-phase cycle tailored to the TRL level. Cycles repeat as needed, typically lasting 4 weeks at TRL4 and 6-8 weeks at TRL6, with timing adjusted for complexity and capacity and in consultation with WP2.

Both TRL4 and TRL6 testing follow a common cycle, with the phases being:

1. **Assessment:** Evaluators test the testing package against acceptance criteria and across feedback dimensions.
 - a. TRL4: 2 weeks
 - b. TRL6: 3 weeks
2. **Synthesis:** test results are organised and aggregated during a two week period before handover to WP2.
 - a. TRL4: 2 weeks (overlapping)
 - b. TRL6: 3 weeks
3. **Revision:** WP2 implements changes via coordination meetings and workflows.
 - a. TRL4: 2 weeks (overlapping): Quick fixes for critical issues, flagging larger issues
 - b. TRL6: 4 weeks
4. **Validation:** Services retested to verify fixes and readiness.
 - a. TRL4: 1 week
 - b. TRL6: 2-3 weeks

Testing within each discipline or test package proceeds independently to respect project timelines and capacity. Synchronisation points (e.g. workshops, webinars, reviews) promote alignment and knowledge sharing. Testing teams can help schedule domain-specific validation windows while maintaining coherence with the overall timeline. Regular task meetings (e.g., bi-weekly) track progress, address technical challenges, and support participants. These sessions facilitate alignment on scope, course corrections, and resource allocation. The coordination and facilitation team may adjust modality in response to emerging patterns or unforeseen challenges.

3.2.4 Where Testing Takes Place

GitHub and Jira serve as the central repository for ticket management and issue reporting. As needed we will develop standardised templates with custom fields to capture all relevant pilot outcomes. GitHub handles

code-related tracking and version control and issue reporting/mitigation, and Jira handles requirements, specifications and development progression. The suggested establishment of a Component Inventory would consolidate traceability information linking observations to evidence and acceptance criteria.

The project-internal Wiki (procedures, FAQs, technical specifications), and regular coordination meetings facilitate clarifications, technical guidance, and exchange between WP2 development teams and the testing teams.

For TRL6, helpdesk or office hours may support tester onboarding and issue resolution. Communication protocols for issue resolution and feature adjustment can be established via GitHub issues or Jira tickets, with development representatives potentially participating in meetings during testing.

For services and tools, testing needs to happen in a *test environment*:

- **TRL4:** Controlled environments within EOSC EDEN consortium settings using representative test datasets (Section 3.1.3) and sandboxes will have to be provided by WP2 and facilitated by WP5, to allow evaluators to assess basic service functionality.
- **TRL6:** At this TRL, testing environments are expected to be approaching real-world digital preservation environments across multiple disciplines, not just in "laboratory" settings. Hence, including diverse datasets that vary in quality, volume, and discipline, integration with existing preservation workflows, and cross-disciplinary scenarios, would ensure adaptability to different contexts, resources, and future requirements.

Platform selection prioritises existing tools (Jira, Google Docs, GitHub) to minimise technical overhead, ensure participant familiarity, and simplify access management for broader audiences at TRL6.

3.3 Acceptance Criteria

User acceptance criteria are a key component in the software development cycle as they allow to assess if the tool that is being tested achieves or not its user goals [4]. In this section, we outline principles to help us formulate the acceptance criteria to assess the acceptability of the registry and services developed by WP2. We stress that the actual Criteria will be co-developed together with WP2 when the development work will be more defined, as these Criteria will have a close relation with the functional requirements selected for development.

When formulating the acceptance criteria, we should follow these guidelines:

- Criteria should be clear, concise and jargon neutral.
- They should be measurable and testable statements which verify the validity of the functionality.
- They should focus on the goal of the functionality and not on the form of the solution.

WP2 will release their outputs at two different TRLs, which will be reflected in the acceptance criteria:

- TRL4 is an "alpha test", to verify that the service is on the right development track. The testing will focus on core service functionality, basic workflow integration, and preliminary usability within the EOSC EDEN project.
- TRL6 will test functional levels as a beta release of the service, verifying the performance of the system in relevant environments that reflect real world constraints.

Close collaboration between the testing and development team is needed to define TRL6 more specifically. We recommend for the project to discuss and adopt a project-wide definition of TRL6, to be used as additional criteria when evaluating the final WP2 outputs.

We list here some example assessment questions that would help guide us in defining and evaluating the acceptance of the registry and services:

- Does the service deliver on the goals of the core functionalities?
- Can the intended users use the service? I.e., is the tool fit for purpose?
- Can each discipline use the service?
- Is it possible to identify which workflows can utilise the core functionalities? I.e., where does the service/tool fit in your daily workflows?
- Do the service functionalities fit the needs of the users? I.e., do the functionalities satisfy use cases¹¹?
- Are there any “showstoppers” (critical issues/major bugs which should be fixed)?

The answer to these questions may be different for each discipline and may need to be recorded on a sliding (Likert¹²) scale rather than in a binary (positive/negative) way. We stress that if the testing with the different disciplines results in different outcomes for these assessment questions, this may not lead to a rejection of the tested tool, but it could instead feed into the Support Kit (Section 4.3). If the tool is suitable for the majority of the early adopter disciplines, it will be accepted but additional guidance may be needed to better define its applicability. The results of the acceptance criteria evaluation for the WP2 outputs will be provided to the development teams via the proposed Component Inventory (see Section 1.2).

3.4 Feedback Dimensions

In this section, we describe how feedback about any aspect that is not contemplated in the acceptance criteria will be provided. We divide our feedback dimensions into two main categories that reflect the type of item assessed, i.e. “Services and Tools” and “Reports and Software Documentation”. The specific approaches used are then adapted based on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the technology being assessed and the characteristics of the service being delivered.

Alignment with the Reuse Fitness Model (Figure 2), the UJMs and the CPPs will also be considered during feedback work.

In what follows, we provide a limited number of examples to contextualise the feedback procedure, all while being aware that the shape and nature of the actual feedback will depend on the specific characteristics of the output considered.

3.4.1 Services and Tools

MS5 - First release (MVP) (TRL4) of registry, deposit guidance, and automated curation services, use case service implementation

Feedback will be given on all services and tools from a discipline-oriented perspective. The testing teams will focus on capturing any discipline-specific variations with the overarching goal to establish a foundational understanding of cross-disciplinary applicability. Comprehensive validation is deferred to later stages.

¹¹ Use cases will be both provided by the development teams and extracted from the relevant UJMs.

¹² A Likert scale is a psychometric scale usually invoked in surveys to measure attitudes. In this context, we will adopt it to measure success or adoption capability of an output/metric, typically by assigning numerical values to qualitative descriptions (1: not capable to 5: fully capable).

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Likert_EDENE

The planned procedure is as follows:

1. The testing teams will consider both functional and non-functional aspects.
2. The testing teams will suggest the implementation of identified new key features (i.e., new functional requirements) that were not anticipated before and tailored to the domain-specific needs.
3. As a result, these new features can be considered for the beta release (MS7). For new non-functional requirements, feedback will be provided on the relevance of aspects such as:
 - a. performance, security, usability, maintainability, scalability and reliability;
 - b. ease of setting up and network bandwidth for data transfer.

At this stage, it is important to note that feedback is drawn upon initial testing outcomes to inform iterative refinements and prepare for subsequent assessment phases.

MS7 - Beta Release - registry, deposit and curation platform, use case service implementations (TRL6)

At TRL6, feedback will focus on performance under practical operational conditions, addressing:

- overall integration of services and registry;
- (cross-disciplinary) interoperability; and
- performance under resource limitations.

Evaluation will focus on:

- how the registry, deposit and curation platform can improve researchers' and repository managers' daily activities by measuring qualitatively the performance gains in activities related to deposit and curation of digital objects; and
- what was materialised from the feedback in the first release at TRL4.

3.4.2 Reports and Software Documentations

For all reports and software documentations produced to achieve milestones MS5 and MS7 and D2.3¹³, feedback will be gathered for several key areas:

- content quality
 - readability
 - clarity and understandability
 - completeness, including coverage of discipline-specific aspects such as recommendations, guidelines, use cases wherever relevant
 - conciseness
 - level of detail
- efficiency
 - reading time
 - comprehensiveness
 - precision
- presentation
 - structure, i.e. logical flow and organisation
 - distribution format

¹³ D2.3: "Final report on the EOSC EDEN registry, services and related selection guidance".

3.4.3 Delivery of Feedback

After feedback is produced by the testing teams, it will be checked and edited by the test coordinators, following a standardised feedback form. The feedback will be delivered to the development teams via the Component Inventory (Section 1.2).

4 Value of Pilot Methodology for Work Package 3

Work Package 3 is responsible for the discipline-specific perspective in EOSC EDEN and is as such tasked with analysing the current state of the art of LTP in the disciplinary communities, validating the outputs of the project and creating supporting material for the future adoption of LTP practices and tools.

The Pilot Methodology of T3.2 does not strictly include testing the outputs of WP3 in the same structured way adopted for the outputs of WP1 and WP2. Nonetheless, we identify points of contact and synergies between the application of this Methodology and the work being undertaken in WP3, some of which we address below.

4.1 Task 3.1 Collaboration

The partners in T3.1 have been tasked with the analysis of the LTP landscape to define requirements and needs for active preservation and quality management of digital objects. The first iteration of requirement gathering work has already been performed, using a combination of desk-based mapping, interviews with repository personnel and researchers, and questions integrated into a survey executed by T1.1 in summer 2025. This work is reported in the WP3 deliverable D3.1 [5]. As indicated above, the T3.1 requirement gathering work is envisioned to be refined during the duration of the EOSC EDEN project. In this sense, the results of the pilot testing from each discipline, together with the UJMs, can contribute to strengthening the understanding of the existing gaps in LTP practices, and can help prioritise which requirements should have higher priority in the project. Additionally, practical engagement with the WP1 and WP2 outputs via application of the Methodology may reveal information about requirements and needs that were not captured in the initial round of requirements gathering. Tight collaboration between T3.2 and T3.1 will result in a structured and richer understanding of the discipline-specific and cross-disciplinary requirement landscape.

4.2 Task 3.2 Feedback Loop

As already mentioned, the Pilot Methodology has been created when the development work of WP1 and WP2 was still in its initial stage. We have put effort into creating a framework that is defined enough for our testing teams to have a solid structure to rely on, while maintaining a necessary degree of flexibility to adapt the Pilot Methodology to the output to be tested. Given this, we will be seeking and receiving feedback on the Pilot Methodology itself both from our own testing teams, and from the WPs that developed the outputs being tested¹⁴.

We will be interested in receiving feedback on the practicalities of the methodology, e.g., was the testing period long enough? Was the supporting material detailed enough? Did the WPs provide sufficient assistance to the testing teams?

These learning moments will be especially important for the testing of the WP2 outputs, since these will be tested in two rounds (TRL4 and TRL6). This means that after the first round of testing at TRL4, we will be able to reflect and course-correct when necessary for the testing of the same items at TRL6.

¹⁴ If the feedback on the Pilot Methodology is substantial enough to warrant a modification of this document, we will publish an amended version to the same Zenodo deposit, with clear versioning. The intention of this is to provide as complete a methodology as possible, after the end of the project.

4.3 Task 3.3 Support Kit

Task 3.3 is responsible for developing a Support Kit for the different discipline- and data type-oriented communities, which will empower them to adopt (and where needed, adapt) and extend the framework, tools and services developed in the EOSC EDEN project.

The testing phases will allow us to understand where the end-users will need more support in utilising the EOSC EDEN outputs. This means that closely following the testing teams during piloting will provide valuable input for T3.3 in their work (starting in March 2026 - M15). T3.3 members will therefore be included in the testing teams when possible, and will also receive from T3.2 notes, log-books and other relevant and useful assets produced during the testing periods.

5 Conclusions

This section offers a summary of the present deliverable as well as a quick reference to the Pilot Methodology to facilitate use during pilot setups.

5.1 Summary

In this document, we have described the Pilot Methodology that T3.2 of WP3 will follow in testing the outputs of the EOSC EDEN project. We have outlined the expected nature of the outputs of both WP1 and WP2 - considering all available information at the time of writing, and the operational workflows to test them. We have described the discipline-specific nature of the user-testing and underlined how the pilots need to be adapted to each of the seven early adopter disciplines of the EOSC EDEN project with the inclusion of domain-specific test datasets and use cases. Finally, we have presented the guiding principles we will follow in defining user acceptance criteria for the testing and the different dimensions which we will provide feedback on to the development teams.

This document has been written when part of the development work is still in its early phases. We have therefore stressed how the details of the testing procedure will have to be co-designed with the development teams when the development work is more advanced, to guarantee coherence with the nature of the outputs and completeness in evaluating them. Coordination between WP1, WP2 and WP3 is already in place and we will enhance it with ad hoc coordination between T3.2 and the development teams. Additionally, we suggest the creation of a Component Inventory where to record all information for each developed output and which will act as a single source of truth.

As a final remark, while drafting this deliverable we have recognised that TRLs levels are not yet defined in the project, relying for now on their common definition [2].

While TRL4 ("technology validated in lab" [2]) is a low barrier for continued development work and can be verified straightforwardly in the first round of pilot testing, for TRL6 ("technology demonstrated in relevant environment" [2]), there is a need for a more precise definition at the EOSC EDEN project level.

Such a project-wide definition of TRL6 will act as an ulterior acceptance criteria for the outputs of WP2 at their final release.

5.2 Pilot Methodology Quick Reference

We have summarised in Table 1 below the steps of the Pilot Methodology, including the most relevant actions to take and their expected duration, the stakeholders involved and the key outputs. This table can act as a quick reference for the application of the Methodology.

Table 1 – Pilot Methodology quick reference

Phase	Duration	Actions	Stakeholders	Outputs
Preparation	3-4 weeks before testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare handoff of testing materials - Prepare discipline-specific support material - Conduct briefing sessions - Define acceptance criteria - Set up testing teams 	Development teams, test coordinators, domain specialists	Complete testing package
Testing	2-6 weeks, depending on TRL and complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate testing package against acceptance criteria and across feedback dimensions - Evidence collection 	Testing teams, possibly, broader community via WP4/FIDELIS partnership and coordination	Test artifacts, assessment results
Synthesis	2 weeks (overlapping)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise and synthesise feedback - Identify common patterns across disciplines - Prepare feedback report - Deliver feedback to development teams 	Testing teams	Synthesised feedback report
Revision	2-3 weeks depending on TRL and complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement changes to output - Coordination meetings - Track updates (Jira, GitHub) 	Development teams	Revised outputs
Validation	1-3 weeks, depending on TRL and complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verify issue resolution - Final acceptance decision - Document lessons learned 	Testing teams	Final assessment

6 References

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